

A Descriptive Study on Histopathology of Fallopian Tubes Obtained at Tertiary Care Hospital in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital, West BengalKomal Toshniwal¹, Sambit Kar², Abhijit Pahari³, Ayon Mitra⁴, Barsha Subhadarshine⁵, Kalyan Khan⁶, Siddhartha Datta⁷^{1,3}Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Haldia 721645, West Bengal^{2,4}Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Haldia 721645, West Bengal⁵Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Haldia 721645, West Bengal⁶Professor and MSVP, Department of Pathology, Jalpaiguri Government Medical College and Hospital, Jalpaiguri, West Bengal⁷Professor and Head, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, North Bengal Medical College & Hospital, Sushruta Nagar, Dist Darjeeling, West Bengal 734012

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Abstract:**Background:** Fallopian tubes are affected by a wide spectrum of diseases varying from salpingitis to carcinoma. Extensive review of the worldwide web and relevant texts revealed scant data about these diseases of fallopian tubes. This lacuna prompted us to vigorously pursue and shed some light on the topic, especially in this part of India. Therefore, descriptive study on histopathology of fallopian tube was done at department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, North Bengal Medical College, West Bengal to identify the various diseases of fallopian tube.**Materials & Methods:** This descriptive observational study was done over a period of one year (May 2018–April 2019) in women who had salpingectomy and tubal ligation at NBMCH. Specimens of salpingectomy from clients who underwent, tubal ligation or along with hysterectomy/oophorectomy were taken. All surgeries were performed in the Gynaecology OT of NBMCH, West Bengal. Ligation was done by Parkland Method or by modified Pomeroy method. Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral or unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy due to various indications was done in usual procedure. Only salpingo-oophorectomy was also done in a case of ovarian torsion. In cases of ectopic pregnancy total or partial salpingectomy was done. Gross abnormalities like paratubal cysts were encouraged to be taken in the specimen. Specimen was then preserved in 10% formalin, labelled properly and taken to Pathology Department of NBMCH.**Results:** It is evident from this table that most common histological finding was of normal fallopian tubes, approximately 70% (71 specimens). Approx 61 specimens were of fallopian tube only. The remaining 10 were composite specimen of uterus with cervix and bilateral normal fallopian tubes. Chronic nonspecific salpingitis is the commonest amongst other pathologies followed closely by tubal ectopic pregnancy. Tubal gestation without the features of salpingitis was more common in the age group of 31-40 years.**Conclusion:** Majority of the tubes had normal appearance on histopathology (approximately 70%). In the remaining proportion, most common pathological lesion was chronic non-specific salpingitis (9.8%). Amongst cases of ruptured tubal ectopic pregnancy 44.4% were associated with chronic salpingitis.**Keywords:** Fallopian tube, histopathology, salpingitis, tubal ligation, hysterectomy, bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy.

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Introduction

Fallopian tube is named after Gabriele Falloppio, a 16th century Italian physician and surgeon who was expert in anatomy, physiology and pharmacology [1]. Each tube measures 7 to 12 cm in length. The tube is divided into four parts - The interstitial portion passes through the body of the uterus at the cornu. The isthmic portion begins adjacent to the

uterine corpus. It consists of a narrow lumen and a thick muscular wall. The ampullary portion is recognized as the lumen of the isthmic portion of the tube widens. In addition, this segment has a more convoluted mucosa. The fimbriated portion is the distal continuation of the ampullary segment. The fimbriated end has many fronds like projections that

provide a wide surface area for ovum pickup. The fimbria ovarica is the extension that contacts the ovary [2]. Fallopian tubes pick up the ovum from pelvic cavity and act as conduit from ovary to uterus. Fertilization of ovum occurs in ampullary segment of the tube [3]. Any change in the structure of fallopian tube can hamper this physiological function and lead to infertility. Also the cyclic hormonal changes in child bearing age group of female lead to changes in histology of fallopian tube and any abnormality there leads to infertility with its complications [4].

Fallopian tubes are affected by a wide spectrum of diseases varying from salpingitis to carcinoma. Traditionally diagnosis of PID is based on triad of symptoms and signs, including pelvic pain, cervical motion tenderness, and the presence of fever. It is recognized that there is wide variation in many symptoms and signs among women with this condition, which makes the diagnosis of PID difficult. Many women with PID exhibit subtle symptoms and signs that are not readily recognized as PID. Some women may develop PID without having any symptoms [5]. This study was aimed at looking the occurrence of chronic asymptomatic salpingitis amongst other histopathological findings of fallopian tube.

Although fallopian tubes are common surgical specimen in pathology laboratory but its histology is sporadically described in literature. Routine histopathological studies of fallopian tube specimen are necessary as many important lesions may be missed clinically, which might have direct bearing on the patient's further management and follow up. Extensive review of the worldwide web and relevant texts revealed scant data about these diseases of fallopian tubes. This lacuna prompted us to vigorously pursue and shed some light on the topic, especially in this part of India. Therefore, descriptive study on histopathology of fallopian tube was done at department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, North Bengal medical college from May 2018 to April 2019 to identify the various diseases of fallopian tube.

General Objective:

- To study the gross and microscopic features of the excised fallopian tubes and to study the common and unusual lesions in them.

Specific Objectives:

- To calculate the occurrence of chronic asymptomatic salpingitis.
- To study the frequency of different histopathological findings.

Materials and Methods

This descriptive observational study was done at Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, North Bengal Medical College & Hospital; district Darjeeling over a period of one year (May 2018– April 2019). Study Population was women who had

salpingectomy and tubal ligation at NBMCH. Specimens of salpingectomy from clients who underwent, tubal ligation or along with hysterectomy/oophorectomy were taken.

$$\text{Sample size: } n = 2\alpha^2 P(1-P)/D^2$$

α is type 1 error, value is 1.96 if p is taken as <0.05

P is prevalence = 42% (from a similar type of study) [6]

D is absolute error = 10% (to be decided by the researcher)

In a study, out of the 382 fallopian tube specimens, 223 cases (58.4%) were normal, whereas 159 cases (41.6%) fallopian tubes were abnormal. Of the abnormal fallopian tube specimens, the most common histopathological finding observed were inflammatory conditions seen in 61/159 (16%) of the fallopian tubes seen most commonly in the age group of 21-40 years [6]. So, using this reference we will calculate the sample size as follow: $3.84 \times 42 \times 58/10 \times 10 = 93$.

Taking into consideration the fall out, we added 10% extra to the sample size. So the final sample size came to be 102.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Clients undergoing tubal ligation.
- Patients having salpingectomy for ectopic pregnancy.
- Patients having hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients having gross features or USG findings of PID like obvious hydrosalpinx.
- Fallopian tube tissue received which are insufficient for opinion are excluded.

A separate proforma was filled for each patient after taking proper consent.

Technique of obtaining the tube: All surgeries were performed in the Gynaecology OT of NBMCH, West Bengal. Ligation was done by Parkland Method or by modified Pomeroy method. Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral or unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy due to various indications was done in usual procedure. Only salpingo-oophorectomy was also done in a case of ovarian torsion. In cases of ectopic pregnancy total or partial salpingectomy was done. Gross abnormalities like paratubal cysts were encouraged to be taken in the specimen. Specimen was then preserved in 10% formalin, labelled properly and taken to Pathology Department of NBMCH.

Grossing and slide preparation: During grossing of fallopian tube, length of each fallopian tube was recorded. The presence of any gross external

abnormality such as rupture, cyst, nodule or tumour was noted. The grossly normal fallopian tube was serially sectioned at 3 to 5 mm interval. On 1st day the cut section of fallopian tube was kept in fixative neutral buffered 10% formaldehyde for 24 hours. Then on 2nd day it was kept in 50% alcohol for 2 hours, 70% alcohol for 2 hours and in 90% alcohol for overnight. Then on 3rd day it was placed first in absolute alcohol- I for 60 minutes, then absolute alcohol- II for 60 minutes, xylene (I), xylene (II) for 60 minutes each & finally in the paraffin I for 60 minutes. On 4th day after removing the tissue from paraffin (I) it was kept in paraffin (II) for 60 minutes and paraffin (III) for 60 minutes. Then the tissue containing paraffin block was cut by microtome. Then the tissue ribbon was placed in slide with the help of water bath. Then staining was done. First the slide was placed in incubator at 37 degree celsius for 10 to 15 minutes. Then it was placed in xylene (I) for 10 minutes & xylene (II) for 10 minutes respectively. Then it is dipped in 90% alcohol for 4 to 5 minutes, 70% alcohol for 5 minutes & 50% alcohol for 5 minutes. Then the slide was placed in

haematoxylin solution for 3 to 4 minutes. It was used for the demonstration of cell nuclei. Then washing of the slide was done with running tap water and the slide took blue colour. Next it was dipped in 2% acid alcohol & finally it was washed under running water before placing it in eosin. Eosin, a red dye properly used on well-fixed material stains connective tissue and cytoplasm in varying intensity. About 3-4 dips were usually made in eosin solution. Slight over staining with eosin is removed while passing through serial dilution of alcohol. Then it was air dried. Mounting made by cover slip with one drop of Canada balsum and it was ready for observation under microscope and the slide was studied under 10 X, 40 X and 100 X magnifications.

Results

A total of 102 cases were selected for our study. Most of the tubal specimens were bilateral (94.1%). Only in 6 cases we did a unilateral salpingectomy. For all the bilateral cases the histological findings were same in both the tubes.

Table 1: Shows distribution of cases according to the surgery performed

Operative indication	Number (n=102)	Percentage
C/S with ligation	62	60.7
Interval ligation	7	6.8
Puerperal ligation	2	1.9
MTP ligation	10	9.8
Ectopic pregnancy	9	8.8
Fibroid uterus	5	4.9
Adenomyosis	4	3.9
Ovarian torsion	1	0.9
CA ovary	2	1.9

Out of 102 cases, maximum cases (81) were contributed by ligation, ligation done during the caesarean being the highest.

11 cases were of total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (TAH with BSO) due to fibroid, adenomyosis and malignant ovarian

tumour. There were 9 cases of ruptured ectopic pregnancy and in 4 of them ligation of the other tube was also done.

1 case of ovarian torsion was operated for which unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was done [Table 1].

Table 2: Showing frequency of various histological finding

Histopathological finding	Number	Percentage
Normal fallopian tube	61	59.8
Chronic non-specific salpingitis	10	9.8
Tubal pregnancy	9	8.8
Para tubal cyst	6	5.8
Tubal congestion	3	2.9
Decidual cells in fallopian tube	2	1.9
Hydrosalpinx	2	1.9
Haematosalpinx	1	0.9
Plical edema and telengectasia	1	0.9
Composite specimen		
Leiomyoma uterus, tubes normal	4	3.9
Leiomyoma uterus, tubal endometriosis	1	0.9
Adenomyotic uterus, tubes normal	3	2.9
Serous cystadenoma of ovary with tube normal	1	0.9

Borderline mucinous tumour with tube normal	1	0.9
Broad ligament leiomyoma with adenomyotic uterus with paratubal cyst	1	0.9
Serous carcinoma right ovary with tubal infiltration	1	0.9

It is evident from this table that most common histological finding was of normal fallopian tubes, approximately 70% (71 specimens). Approx 61 specimens were of fallopian tube only. The remaining 10 were composite specimen of uterus with cervix and bilateral normal fallopian tubes. Out of these 10, 5 had leiomyoma uterus, 3 had adenomyosis, 2 cases were of ovarian tumour- one had serous cystadenoma and the other had borderline mucinous tumour.

The next in row is chronic nonspecific salpingitis which accounts for 9.8% of the various histological findings. Of the total 10 cases, 6 were obtained after ligation, and the remaining 4 had ectopic pregnancy with the background of chronic salpingitis on histology. About 9 cases showed the features of tubal

gestation i.e. chorionic villi with areas of haemorrhage. The following pie diagram is showing the distribution of tubal ectopic with other background histological findings [Table 2; Fig 2-13]. Of the 7 cases of para tubal cyst, one was associated with broad ligament leiomyoma and the remaining were seen with ligation specimen.

Three (3) cases showed tubal congestion. 2 cases were of hydrosalpinx and decidual cells in the fallopian tube each. Only 1 case each of haematosalpinx and plical edema were noted. Single case of tubal endometriosis was noted associated with uterine leiomyoma. However, there were no cases of primary malignancy of the fallopian tube; a single case of secondary tubal infiltration due to serous carcinoma of right ovary was noted [Fig. 1].

Figure 1: Various histologies with tubal ligation

Images of various histological findings obtained during the study

Figure 2: Fallopian tube normal structures- intraluminal plicae and subepithelial muscular layer, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 3: Ciliated epithelium – fallopian tube, high power 40 X, H & E stain.

Figure 4: Fallopian tube – blunted plicae, subepithelial sclerosis and moderate intramural chronic inflammation – chronic nonspecific salpingitis, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 5: Nonspecific salpingitis in a case of ruptured tubal ectopic pregnancy, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 6: Ectopic pregnancy, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 7: Tubal congestion, high power 40 X, H & E stain.

Figure 8: Intramural islands of atypical pleomorphic, hyperchromatic cuboidal cells in a case of CA ovary with infiltration in fallopian tube, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 9: Haematosalpinx, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 10: Hydrosalpinx, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 11: Para tubal cyst, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 12: Walthard cell nest, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Figure 13: Tubal endometriosis, low power 10 X, H & E stain.

Table 3: Age wise distribution of tubal histology (mean age – 29.4years, SD – 7.9)

Histology	<20 years	21-30	31-40	41-50	>50	Total
Normal	1	50	15	3	1	70 (68.6%)
Pathological						
Para tubal cyst	1	2	2	2	-	7
Chronic nonspecific salpingitis	-	5	1	-	-	6
Tubal congestion	-	3	-	-	-	3
Hydrosalpinx	-	2	-	-	-	2
Decidual cells in fallopian tube	-	2	-	-	-	2
Tubal pregnancy (chorionic villi with areas of haemorrhage)	-	1	3	-	-	4
Tubal pregnancy with chronic non-specific salpingitis	-	3	-	-	-	3
Tubal pregnancy with Haematosalpinx	1	-	-	-	-	1
Tubal pregnancy with chronic salpingitis and Walthard cell nest	-	-	1	-	-	1
Plical edema and telengectasia	-	1	-	-	-	1
Tubal endometriosis	-	-	-	1	-	1
Metastatic deposit	-	-	-	-	1	1
Total Pathological lesion	2 (1.9%)	19(18.6%)	7(6.8%)	3(2.9%)	1(0.9%)	32 (31.4%)

Maximum number of tubal specimen was collected in the age group of 21-30 years. About 50 of them had normal tubal histology and 19 had some pathology. Chronic nonspecific salpingitis is the commonest amongst other pathologies followed closely by tubal ectopic pregnancy. Tubal gestation without the features of salpingitis was more common in the age

group of 31-40 years. Only 3 specimens of tubes were present in below 20 age group. One had normal histology, second showed para tubal cyst and lastly a tubal ectopic with haematosalpinx. In cases of more than 40 years of age paratubal cyst, tubal endometriosis and secondary metastatic deposit was seen [Table 3].

Table 4: Operative indication and histology finding

Indication	Normal tubes	Chronic salpingitis	Others
CS with ligation	50 (80.6%)	4 (6.4%)	8
MTP ligation	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	1
Interval ligation	5	-	2
Puerperal ligation	2	-	-
Ectopic pregnancy	4 (44.4%)	4 (44.4%)	1
TAH with BSO	9	-	3

Amongst all cases of ligation done along with caesarean 80% had normal fallopian tube histology whereas only 6.4% had salpingitis.

This proportion of salpingitis is higher in cases of MTP with ligation to around 20%. This is even

higher in case of ectopic pregnancy. The cases of tubal ectopic with chronic salpingitis are equal to the case of ectopic without salpingitis. 44.4% of tubal ectopics had chronic salpingitis in background.

Table 5: Layers of tube involved in cases of salpingitis (10 cases)

Site Involved	Number	Percentage
Endosalpinx involved	10	100%
Myosalpinx involved	5	50%
Serosa involved	3	30%

Of the 10 cases endosalpinx involvement was there in all the cases, i.e. blunting of plicae, tubal congestion etc. 50 % case had myosalpinx involvement, i.e. the presence of round cells, lymphocytes in the walls of tube. Outer serosal involvement (fibrotic thickening) was present in only 30% of cases [Table 5].

Discussion

Fallopian tubes are rare sites of primary disease and their most common afflictions are inflammation, almost always as part of pelvic inflammatory disease [7]. Tubal disease has been held accountable for 30-40% of the cases of female infertility [8]. In a histopathological study of spectrum of lesions encountered in the fallopian tube, it was noted that tubal pathology is present in only 33.48% of the specimens with chronic salpingitis lesions of the tube forming the major group followed by tubal ectopic pregnancies [9]. The incidence of ectopic tubal pregnancy has increased markedly in recent times and it is often the consequence of chronic salpingitis, which is found in nearly half the patients with a reported range of 29-88% [10-11]. In the present study, most cases with fallopian tubes having chronic salpingitis were of the age 21-30 years. In a study [12], tubal ectopic pregnancy was commonly seen in younger age group of 25-29 years. In another study [13], most common age group was 20-29 years. In the present study, tubal ectopic pregnancy was also seen in younger age group of 21-30 years. In a previous study [14], sample was obtained from total

abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy 38.62% of cases. In another study 156, total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was done in 56.12% cases and unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy in 5.88% cases.

In the present study, maximum cases (81) were contributed by ligation, ligation done during the caesarean being the highest (61%). 11 cases were of total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy (TAH with BSO) due to fibroid, adenomyosis and malignant ovarian tumour (9.7%). There were 9 cases (8.8%) of ruptured ectopic pregnancy and in 4 of them ligation of the other tube was also done. One case of ovarian torsion was operated for which unilateral salpingo-oophorectomy was done. Distribution of the cases, in the present study, is different from previous other studies, and focus has been given to the cases of tubal ligation.

In the present study, the percentage of normal fallopian tube specimens was 68.6%. Another studies showed similar finding with percentage of normal fallopian tube specimens being 66.52% [9], 66.67% [15] and 69% [16]. Some study also showed a higher percentage of normal fallopian tubes that is 84.3% of the specimens [17].

In a study [18], majority of tubal ectopic pregnancy had varied histopathological finding associated with it in which the most common was chronic salpingitis seen in 88% of the cases followed by salpingitis

isthmica nodosa in 43% of cases. In another study [12], the most common associated histopathological finding was chronic salpingitis seen in 39% of the cases followed by acute salpingitis in 18% and salpingitis isthmica nodosa in 6% of the cases. The present study was in concordance with above two studies with chronic salpingitis being the most common associated histopathological finding with tubal ectopic pregnancy seen in 44.4% of the cases followed by, haematosalpinx and Walthard cell nests.

In a study [14], most common lesions were inflammatory as salpingitis in 32.5% of the specimens followed by tubal epithelial hyperplasia seen in 10.8% of the specimens. In other study [15] also, the most common lesion was inflammatory (18.34%). The inflammatory lesions here comprised of salpingitis in 10.19%, pyosalpinx in 0.29% and hydrosalpinx in 7.86% of fallopian tube specimens. In the present study, the most common lesions were inflammatory. The inflammatory lesions comprised of chronic salpingitis in 9.8%, and hydrosalpinx in 1.8% of fallopian tube specimens. In all the studies, neoplastic lesions of fallopian tubes are rare finding. In various studies metastatic lesions were seen in 1.4% [14], 3.4% [17] and in 0.2% [19] of the specimens. In the present study, secondary malignancy accounted to 0.9% of specimens.

Conclusion

Samples of fallopian tubes were obtained from 102 patients after proper consent during various surgical procedures most common being tubal ligation and sent for histopathological examination. Majority of the tubes had normal appearance on histopathology (approximately 70%). In the remaining proportion, most common pathological lesion was chronic non-specific salpingitis (9.8%). Amongst cases of ruptured tubal ectopic pregnancy 44.4% were associated with chronic salpingitis.

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